

eDNAAqua-Plan
NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Proceedings of the WP3 Workshop on standards requirements

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Milestone 5

Work Package 3

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Executive summary

On Friday 13th September 2024, WP3 of the eDNAqua-plan project hosted an in-person workshop on the final day of the General Assembly. This brought together participants to discuss standards for genetic reference libraries and environmental DNA (eDNA) data repositories. The workshop was structured into three main sessions. Firstly, invited presenter Till-Hendrik Macher gave an online seminar on the curation of reference databases. Secondly, two sessions of group discussions were held to cover five topics related to reference databases and eDNA repositories. These covered the storage of vouchers, DNA-material and DNA-barcodes, data and associated metadata (1), the taxonomic curation procedures (2), the machine-readable workflows and data standards for interconnectable libraries (3), the pre-processed metadata for eDNA sample collection and sequencing (4) and the processed metadata for eDNA bioinformatic analysis and data submission (5). In a final session, a summary of the different discussions was made to the entire group, which allowed all participants to be updated on the conversations they missed and contribute further to the topics discussed. Overall, the day was marked by engaging discussions across the different sessions. The combination of grouped and general discussions allowed participants to give their insights on the different topics, as well as allowed the different topic leads to get insights from a wide panel of participants. The various discussion points and outcomes are captured in the proceedings. These will serve the two tasks working on data standards for reference databases (T3.1) and eDNA repositories (T3.2) to elaborate their work plan and formulate their recommendations.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
BIOPOLIS	Associação Biopolis
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
ECB	European Central Bank
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMBRC-ERIC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EU	European Union
EV ILVO	Eigen Vermogen Van Het Institut Voor Landbouw - En Visserijonderzoek
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA	General Assembly
IAB	International Advisory Board
IHU	Diethens Panepistimio Ellados
INRAE	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
LifeWatch-ERIC	E-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
NIVA	Norsk Institutt for Vannforskning
SSBE	Seascape Belgium
SU	Sorbonne Université
SYKE	Suomen Ymparistokeskus
UDE	Universitaet Duisburg-Essen
ULOD	Uniwersytet Lodzki
UMINHO	Universidade do Minho
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization
UVEG	Universitat de València
VLIZ	Vlaams Instituut Voor de Zee
WP	Work Package(s)
WU	Wageningen University

1. Introduction

A. Objective

Within eDNAqua-Plan, WP3 is tasked with planning a digital ecosystem that will be fully transparent and interoperable. This will be ensured amongst others by evaluating the existing data standards for reference databases (T3.1) and eDNA repositories (T3.2). The aim is to generate a best practice recommendation for how to develop data products for aquatic biodiversity in Europe, that are sustainable in the long term, and can be reliably used for future biomonitoring efforts. To best elaborate on these recommendations, WP3 prepared several discussion topics and invited the broader eDNAqua-Plan consortium, of which the different areas of expertise would allow valuable discourse, to provide input. These topics cover:

1. The storage of vouchers, DNA-material and DNA-barcodes, data and associated metadata
2. Taxonomic curation procedures
3. Machine-readable workflows and data standards for interconnectable libraries
4. Pre-processed metadata for eDNA sample collection and sequencing.
5. Processed metadata for eDNA bioinformatic analysis and data submission.

The objective of the M3.1. workshop was to foster a lively discussion among participants from both WP3 and the wider eDNAqua-Plan consortium, including the IAB. The outcome of these discussions is captured in the workshop proceedings below. These proceedings will lead to the writing of a new and agreed version of the T3.1 document “Standards for genetic reference libraries” (D3.1 report) as well as input for the T3.2 document “Report of best practices for eDNA data repositories, including a model of metadata standards alignment” (D3.2). Collectively these are useful for input into the M3.2 milestone for “Workshop for conceptualizing and writing on eDNA data ecosystem”.

B. Overview of the discussion topics

Topic 1. Recommendations for storage of vouchers, DNA-material and DNA-barcodes, data and associated metadata.

In this first topic, we discussed existing and proposed recommendations for DNA harvesting and for the storage of both voucher specimens/samples and genetic data. We also discussed the data and metadata required to ensure the relevance, the accessibility and traceability of DNA data (barcodes, genes, genomes), vouchers and taxonomic identifications.

Topic 2. Taxonomic curation procedures.

The quality of reference libraries relies heavily on the taxonomic accuracy of the reference sequences, and reliable and transparent procedures for curating reference libraries are essential to ensure homogeneous taxonomic names for genetically similar barcodes. Different approaches exist for the expert curation of reference libraries, with each their advantages and caveats. These expert curation procedures can be based on e.g. clustering genetically similar sequences, self-assignment, phylogenies, or the integration of automation and artificial intelligence (AI). In this topic, we were interested in hearing the participants' experience in taxonomic curation as well as their critiques and potential solutions.

Topic 3. Machine-readable workflows and data standards for interconnectable libraries

Interoperability is the ability of computer systems or software to exchange and make use of information. The data usually needs to be integrated with other data. In addition, the data need to interoperate with

applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing [GO FAIR Principles]. Interoperability needs standards; it does not need all systems to use the same standards, but that entities of these standards can be mapped together.

For reference libraries it is particularly important for: 1) knowing the taxonomic entity a record in a reference library applies to and to be able to straightforwardly compare within and between reference libraries and for 2) comparing and contrasting taxonomic assignments. This requires the use of consistent metadata standards, including taxonomies.

Topic 4. Pre-processed metadata for eDNA sample collection and sequencing

This topic addressed the challenges and opportunities in managing eDNA pre-processed (meta)data, captured during sampling and sequencing in metabarcoding studies. Current metadata standards, such as ENA and GSC MxS checklists, were discussed focusing on their effectiveness in documenting essential sampling and laboratory details. Participants identified gaps in these standards and explored ideas to promote adopting standardised metadata practices.

Topic 5. Processed metadata for eDNA bioinformatic analysis and data submission.

This topic addressed the challenges and opportunities in managing eDNA processed (meta)data - the data that results from bioinformatic analysis. Current metadata standards, such as Darwin Core and its DNA-derived extension, were discussed addressing the need for reproducibility of bioinformatics workflow. Participants identified gaps in these standards, particularly in reporting the complexities of bioinformatics processes. The benefits of publishing detailed bioinformatic analysis steps as metadata rather than only describing them in scientific articles were discussed.

C. Workshop Outline

9:00 - 9:15	Welcome
9:15 - 10:30	Online presentation of the dbDNA curation procedure by Till-Hendrik Macher followed by time for questions
10:30 - 10:45	Overall presentation of the different discussion topics
10:45 - 11:30	Coffee break & departure morning participants
11:30 - 12:15	Distribution & Group discussions #1 : Storage and metadata, Curation, Interoperability
12:00 - 13:30	Lunch break
13.30 - 14.45	Distribution & Group discussion #2 Pre-processed, Processed, Curation
14:45 - 15:00	Coffee/Tea Break

15.00 - 17.00	Group restitution of the separate discussions and overall discussion
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The workshop day started with a brief welcome and an online seminar by Till-Hendrik Macher, presenting the dbDNA project, followed by an extensive session of questions and discussion. Next, the morning continued with an overview of the goal and outline of the workshop as well as a presentation of each discussion topic by the topic leads. Several participants could only attend the morning session due to travel constraints, and thus, a first coffee break allowed for some free discussions and goodbyes.

Next, the participants present for the whole day were distributed in different groups, with each group focusing on one discussion topic. Each topic was then discussed in depth among the subgroups of participants to comment on the existing practices and proposals, comment on the gaps already identified, identify new gaps, and generate new ideas.

One group-based discussion session was held before lunch, focusing on the three topics related to reference libraries: the storage of vouchers, DNA, data and metadata, taxonomic curation procedures, and machine-readability and interoperability of reference libraries. A second group-based discussion session was held after lunch, focusing on the two topics related to eDNA: pre-processed eDNA metadata and processed eDNA metadata. Additionally, the topic of reference library curation was repeated for a second time to complete the third discussion group of the afternoon.

During the final session, each topic lead gave a summary of their group discussions to the overall assembly, followed by a general discussion. This allowed participants to provide their insights on the different topics and allowed the different topic leads to get insights from a wide panel of participants.

D. Participants

Participants for the whole day

Ana Camila Babo – BIPOLIS

Filipa Martins – BIOPOLIS

Peter Woollard – EMBL

Frédéric Rimet – INRAE

Ian Probert – SU

Tiina Laamanen – SYKE

Kristian Meissner – SYKE

Michał Grabowski – ULOD

Jenny Giles – CSIRO

Tomasz Rewicz – ULOD

Filipe Costa – UMINHO

Emilie Boulanger – UNESCO

Antonio Camacho – UVEG

Antonio Picazo Mozo – UVEG

Katrina Exter – VLIZ

Pascal Hablützel – VLIZ

Participants only attending the morning seminar

Pier Luigi Buttigieg – AWI

Paulina Ramírez – EMBRC ERIC

Sofie Derycke – EV ILVO

Ioannis Kavakiotis – IHU

Spiros Papakostas – IHU

Oonagh McMeel – SSBE

Karolina Bacela-Spychalska – ULOD

Dawid Krawczyk – ULOD

Tomasz Rewicz – ULOD

Reindert Nijland – WU

Nicolas Pade – EMBRC ERIC

2. Proceedings

A. Presentation of dbDNA by Till-Hendrick Macher

Till-Hendrik Macher was invited to give a presentation on the dbDNA project: “Development of a curated database and analysis infrastructure for DNA-based monitoring in water protection”. dbDNA is a reference database curation and ranking system Till developed during his PhD at the University of Duisburg Essen. His presentation gave the attendants a lot of food for thought, which was evident based on the number of questions asked and the length of the discussion with Till following his presentation. Beyond the discussion following the presentation, several group discussions further cited the curation strategy put forward in the dbDNA project.

dbDNA project

Development of a curated database and analysis infrastructure for DNA-based monitoring in water protection

Till-Hendrik Macher, Arne Beermann, Jens Arle, Jan Koschorreck, Robert Vogl, Peter Rollauffs, Astrid Schmidt-Kloiber, Daniel Hering, Florian Leese

Figure 1. First slide presenting the dbDNA project and its authors.

B. Topic 1: Storage of vouchers, DNA, data and metadata

Lead: Frédéric Rimet

Scribe: Filipa Martins

Present: Antonio Camacho (AC), Michal Grabowski (MG), Filipa Martins (FM), Kristian Meissner (KM), Laamanen Tiina (TL), Tomasz Rewicz (TR), Karolina Bacela (KB) and Frédéric Rimet

Highlights

- **Structure of 3.1 document satisfied the participants.**
- **Amount of the metadata necessary in the reference library depends on the users objectives (routine analysis vs scientific research).**
- **A confidence criteria should be added to barcode taxonomic name.**
- **Interconnectability of databases should enable the access to a large range of metadata.**

First, a round table was proposed, to assess people's experience about reference barcoding libraries. Most of them declared to be contributors and users, and two declared to be an end user of metabarcoding analyses (water managers). The convenor is a user and curator of a library.

Another question was asked by the convenor about the structure given in document 3.1 (Standard for reference libraries), in the section on data and metadata (composed into 4 parts, namely: voucher metadata, biological material metadata, DNA marker metadata, taxonomic information). The participants were satisfied with this and did not see additional parts to add.

A discussion started on the amount of metadata required in the document, which is quite important for some of the participants but necessary for others. For instance, end users (KM, TL) suggested reducing metadata to a minimum in order to have a standard which can be applicable by the maximum of laboratories and in order not to be too expensive to apply: the risk is that stakeholders won't accept it. Other participants of the roundtable (AC, KB) said that it is important to keep as much metadata as possible, because they are important to make the library trustable and usable for scientific research purposes. Further, the more data (e.g. environmental data for ecosystem's samples) can be linked to the sequences through metadata, the higher are the possibilities for data usage for multiple purposes, which makes the effort done to generate the sequences more productive (AC). It emerged that depending on the purpose and the use of the reference library, the diversity and number of metadata needed can differ largely (need much data for research, but maybe less for monitoring purposes).

It was concluded that depending on the target audience, the metadata necessary differed: end-users for monitoring purposes need only minimal metadata, whereas scientists and library curators need the maximum number of metadata. A good balance between curator needs and end users should be found.

Another point was evoked about the diversity of organisms considered. Depending on the organism (fish, insect, microalgae ...), the necessary metadata for library confidence differs. Two strategies are proposed for writing standards (FR): either a list of required and optional metadata can be given for each organism, or a single list of required and optional metadata can be given for whatever the organism is considered. It is proposed to establish a common list to check the metadata systematically mentioned whatever the organism considered (FM).

In addition important points were mentioned:

- It is important to have a metadata field giving the reference (scientific publication) of the barcode (MG), where all necessary information can be found
- It is important to add a metadata field giving the taxonomical confidence/quality of the barcode. Such information should be obtained after running the curation process (TR).
- A standard for DNA data in forensic science has been published (ISO IEC 19794-14); it is important to look at the content of this document, which may serve as inspiration (KM).

The conclusion of these discussions was presented to the general assembly and two additional comments were given.

First, it was explained (Ian Probert) that it is not necessary to gather as many as possible metadata in the reference library since the objective is to have interconnectable databases: for instance, in the case of cultures, most of the metadata listed in the actual document of T3.1 (isolator, sampling date, sampling location, medium ...) can be found in the database of the culture collections. Since these databases and libraries will be interconnectable, it is possible to set the amount of metadata to a minimum. This example can be generalised to other types of vouchers/collections (e.g. natural history collections).

Second, it was also mentioned (Felipe Costa) that it is not necessary to have for all sequences the entire set of metadata since there is a quality/confidence evaluation carried out afterwards by the taxonomic curation (e.g. presentation of Till Macher). The metadata is necessary only in the case of taxonomical discrepancies (which is not systematically the case!) for the curation procedure; if there is not enough

metadata then the sequence will be discarded. However, there was a common agreement that it is important to educate and encourage sequence producers to provide as much metadata as possible when depositing their data.

C. Topic 2: Reference Database Curation

Lead: Ian Probert

Present (over two discussion sessions): Filipe Costa (UMinho) Antonio Picazo (UVEG), Frédéric Rimet (INRAE), Michał Grabowski (ULodz), Tomasz Rewicz (ULodz) and Ian Probert (SU)

Figure 2. A summary of the proposed reference database curation procedures from the discussions under topic 2.

D. Topic 3: Interoperability

Lead: Peter Woollard

Scribe: Emilie Boulanger

Present: Jenny Giles (CSIRO), Katrina Exter (VLIZ), Camila Babo (BIOPOLIS), Pascal Hablützel (VLIZ), Pascal Hablützel (VLIZ) and Peter Woollard (EMBL-EBI)

Highlights:

- Need for standards and awareness on data provenance.
- Different possibilities were discussed to document protocols and workflows.
- Reliability is essential to take into account when defining metadata requirements.
- Need for institute-independent unique identifiers per reference sequence, and standardised marker names.
- The format of the metadata matters for interoperability. Structured forms such as JSON and JSON-LD are both machine- and human-readable

The topic of interoperability was initially introduced to the overall workshop attendants at the beginning of the workshop day during the general introduction. Here, we focus on the aspects of genetic reference libraries (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Flowchart of interoperability between databases.

For the workshop, we initially outlined good scientific data management and stewardship. We then explained what aspects of this **FAIR** encapsulates [Wilkinson 2016]. We proceeded through the FAIR principles in limited detail and further focused on interoperability. (see [GO FAIR](#))

FAIR data has both a machine and a human audience. It was stated that standards are particularly important for machines to be able to deal with data. The context of data is important and we noted that, even data that are restricted (e.g. only open within an organisation) can still be FAIR and should still have FAIR metadata.

It was highlighted that an important aspect of recommendations should focus on the way they are implemented. Data and metadata can be FAIR on the local level, but may not be FAIR in the global context (e.g. the use of standards that no-one else uses or can read/access).

At the vocabulary level, terms should have URLs (which aids interoperability), not only to be rendered to HTML (to ensure machine readability) but also structured text (to allow human readability). The [F-UJI Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool | FAIRsFAIR](#) is used to check FAIRness of metadata that have a URL (as it is a tool that works from a URL). It is open code so can be adapted for particular situations/types of data and hence very hands on as a development and maintenance tool.

We proceeded to discuss **metadata** and which were the most important for interoperability. For these, a central question was asked: what does FAIR mean to you all in relation to reference libraries? One critical aspect is accessibility. Data may not always be, but metadata should be accessible. For some, data + metadata needs to be accessible. It depends on who you are and what your goal is. Given that it is never really possible to have all the metadata in one resource, a suggestion for findability & reusability is to: repeat, trace the steps back one at a time [this is the breadcrumb method].

We also discussed database coverage, and how we could define metadata to flag the level completeness or reference databases. However, it was noted that we cannot really measure completeness. But we can compare between databases to make an assessment on completeness. The completeness of a repository would depend on their scope, which is defined by the repository. This can be defined at multiple levels (scope of the library, scope of each record), and would require metadata about the scope to assess it. It was also noted that reference libraries can never be fully complete. It is then important as a library to alert users about how the completeness of the database will affect them.

Finally, taxonomies are the most important bits of metadata to capture. Typically for eDNA archives the assigned taxonomy is not captured, but rather about the sample e.g. “marine metagenome”. The assigning of the taxonomy is done later in the pipeline data ecosystem.

Provenance and reusability

Fully FAIR data would allow someone to reproduce the experiment (provide enough information that this is possible). Such data should include metadata that points to the provenance of the data, which for a dataset could be a README.txt or provenance-metadata.json file that is provided along with the research data files. All participants noted that sufficient relevant metadata to provenance and reusability is rarely provided as it is hard to collect, mainly because researchers do not realise that they have to collect such information as they do their experimental work! It is also hard to structure in forms as the specifics of provenance varies across types of data, but it is possible to come up with a checklist of provenance fields that 80% of data providers should be able to fill in.

We had a lively discussion about protocols. Ideally, protocols should be versioned so people can easily discern the version of pipelines or protocols that were used. Some of the attendees had been testing out protocols.io but that is largely freeform. The need for machine-readable workflows was expressed. This is being worked on with [bebop](#) for example. In principle, we can make them machine readable and interoperable, but we need to come up with a vocabulary. Someone has to create an ontology for protocols. This is doable, but has to be done.

First step is whether the protocols can be found. Protocols.io is well used and provides a DOI in the metadata. [BioCompute Objects](#) were mentioned, but that is more for the bioinformatics workflows. After the event the ELIXIR [WorkflowHub](#) was raised as a possible solution for both the laboratory and the bioinformatics workflows.

The issue was raised that whole protocols cannot be captured in metadata, and human-readable free text is still needed. The focus should then be on picking out important aspects (e.g. that people will want to search on, perhaps) and making those provenance metadata with defined vocabulary terms. In Wildlife Australia the ISO standards being used are very strict, but makes it hard from a user perspective

Reliability was discussed as essential to take into account when defining metadata requirements. There are so many sources of potential error possible. It is important that metadata criteria are included, that would allow reference database users to evaluate the reliability of the data sources, and in doing so quantify the trust they can have in the data. One avenue would be to include a rating into the database curation step, as presented in the dbDNA project during the morning sessions. The concern was however raised that a rating makes a lot of assumptions, and relies much on man-made choices for phylogeny.

If they provide provenance to produce an object (where source material comes from), then they need to pick out particular metadata to flag that. E.g. Is the protocol published. Adding a DOI referencing the

published paper associated with deposited DNA sequences can allow us to evaluate the reliability of a data submission. It can show for example that the data is part of an extremely reliable phylogeny instead of just a random sequencing project.

Is it useful to capture a phylogenetic tree? Answer from the group: Phylogeny cannot be captured as metadata, but can be considered as provenance. It is too unstable and after some time it gets unimportant. It will also depend on which markers were used. The consensus was that it is not particularly important. The question was raised because this information occurs in some genetic ref libs.

Unique Identifiers

The question of whether unique identifiers are needed was raised. Often, identifiers are institute-specific which hinders their use across databases outside of the institute. A solution could be to use the [ULID \(Universally Unique Lexicographically Sortable Identifier\)](#) which can be generated and is unique. It basically acts as a timestamp. Australia's National Biodiversity DNA Library (NBDL) have adapted ULID for their purpose and will soon publish their methods to be reused.

The unique ID should not just point to a specimen but point to the instance of sequencing that specimen. Because if a specimen is resequenced, the results can be different again. So each sequence needs a unique identifier. It was stressed that it is very important to make sure identifiers are really unique to maintain the integrity of the connections between all data and metadata.

Barcode Marker Names

The topic of lack of standardisation in MarkerNames was raised. Some are using the human/vertebrate (HGN/VGN) standards. Different people have different ways to call markers etc. Users need guidance on this.

JSON and JSON-LD

Next, different data and metadata formats were discussed. The format of the metadata matters for interoperability, a structured form such as JSON and for even better [JSON-LD](#) (as uses [schema.org](#)).

If the Darwin Core (DwC) standards are followed, the information on the origin of the data is in the data file itself and not in the metadata file. To harvest and use this metadata, there is a need to understand the data. Certain formats do this in a machine-readable way e.g. JSON

JSON and JSON-LD are human and machine readable metadata. They are also used to communicate data. JSON is a more human readable format compared to XML which had been used in previous decades. JSON-LD is the implementation of linked-data concepts in JSON, making it more semantically understandable for humans and machines.

Figure 4. Notes taken by participants during the session on interoperability for genetic reference libraries.

In summary:

- The most important metadata for total genetics reference library were:
 - The geographic coverage: countries and environments
 - Taxonomic coverage
 - Accessibility: Is it open access or closed?
- The most important metadata about a genetics reference individual record were:
 - The identified organism taxonomy of a record in CURIE format or persistent identifier.
 - Need unique identifiers for all the reference barcode sequences: ULID provides this whether internal or public.
 - Markername, make it standardised.e.g. HGN/VGN nomenclature
 - Provenance of the sample/specimen voucher.

- Having all steps of protocol is difficult. But provenance is a good way to go.
 - DOI - of protocol or paper: indicates that it is a sound study with good effort to record workflows et..
 - Reliability of the barcode: e.g specificity of a barcode to a species and choices made
- The format of the metadata matters for interoperability: a structured form such as JSON and even better [JSON-LD](#) (as uses [schema.org](#)) is good for both machines and human brains.

Bibliography

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- [GO FAIR](#)
- [F-UJI Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool | FAIRsFAIR](#)
- [ULID \(Universally Unique Lexicographically Sortable Identifier\)](#)
- [Protocols.io](#) (well established, now commercial+freeform, lab and bioinformatics) ,
- [WorkflowHub](#) (ELIXIR: lab + bioinformatics)
- [BioCompute Objects](#) (just bioinformatics)
- [JSON-LD](#)
- [schema.org](#)

E. Topic 4: Pre-processed eDNA Metadata

Lead: Filipa Martins

Scribe: Emilie Boulanger

Present: Antonio Picazo (UVEG), Tiina Laemanen (SYKE), Kristian Meissner (SYKE), Filipa Martins (BIOPOLIS) and Emilie Boulanger (UNESCO)

Highlights:

- **eDNA data is currently not truly reusable.**
- **Systems to publish eDNA data need to be made easier.**
- **We need to build on existing requirements rather than reinventing them.**
- **Ways forward – ideas for implementing better practices were proposed.**

This workshop group was focused on discussing the metadata required for pre-processed eDNA data. Pre-processed eDNA data consists of raw metabarcoding sequencing reads before any bioinformatics processing is applied. The metadata accompanying pre-processed eDNA data covers all the steps of the eDNA metabarcoding workflow from sampling until sequencing.

The participants were distributed at the beginning of the session and represented data generators (Antonio Picazo, Filipa Martins), data publishers (Emilie Boulanger) and data users for policy (Kristian Meissner, Tiina Laemanen). The session was started by proposing an initial question to the participants, “Based on your experience, what are the most significant challenges or gaps in the current(meta)data

management and sharing practices?”, from which the discussion followed its course. Several major topics were raised over the course of the discussion.

From the start, participants highlighted that eDNA data is currently being published under the impression of adhering to FAIR standards, but is in reality not truly reusable. Key information is missing to make the data not only reusable but also trustworthy. There should be a big focus on metadata that is essential for trust.

Participants noted that one essential step to document in the workflow that needs clear metadata reporting to make the data trustworthy: is the sampling. Clear metadata should be reported on how samples were collected and whether standards were followed for storage. If existing ISO standards are followed by the agency doing the field and lab work, these can be referenced to have the necessary information. It was however noted at the restitution session at the end of the day, that ISO standards are not research protocols and adequate documentation will still be necessary for key steps.

Participants were asked about their experience in publishing eDNA data to public repositories. Based on their experience, differences were raised between existing sequence repositories. On one side, NCBI requires only a little mandatory information (name, coordinates, matrix). This makes it easier to publish your data, but also easier to omit any metadata that will ensure the data is reusable. Note that data is typically published to public repositories because authors are required to do so upon publishing their paper, and the accompanying metadata is then often limited to the minimum requirements. EMBL’s ENA on the other side requests more metadata in the form of specific checklists to be filled out. These require more work from the data publishers, but also offer more structure and ensure more of the essential metadata is captured. However, existing ENA checklists do not cover the full range of eDNA assays.

To ensure more of the necessary metadata is provided upon publishing eDNA data, one option would be to make more fields mandatory, but adjusted to the eDNA assay. The participants also noted that in order to promote metadata publishing, the systems to do so need to be made easier. For example, GBIF has an excel template which makes it easier to format data and facilitates data publishing. However, open fields must be avoided. Participants mentioned that checklists and standards should have standardised answers selectable from a drop-down field that are accompanied by a clear description. It was noted that the relevant existing standards (e.g. Darwin Core and MlxS) do indeed have well-defined terms, which is a good thing. However, there is guidance needed on which standards need to be applied to what data in which repository. There are currently too many places to put data, and data generators often do not know where to go.

Most importantly, we don’t need to re-invent new standards. Instead, we should build as much as possible on existing standards and requirements. The European Water Framework Directive already requires a set of essential sampling -information. When writing eDNA-specific metadata standards, we should base ourselves on the existing metadata requirements for existing monitoring methods. These are also already thought out to cover different environments and target organisms, particularly for sampling. The participants additionally highlighted that the Darwin Core standards were not made with the EU directive in mind but instead focus on research. Here, we should focus as well on an implementation outcome and keep the EU commission’s perspective in mind.

This workshop session also came up with a few ideas for different eDNAqua-Plan Work Packages. The use cases in WP4 are currently focusing on publishing datasets to identify gaps in requirements. They are thus approaching this from a data-publisher perspective, but could also approach this from a data-user perspective. They could then go harvest public datasets, try to analyse them and note down what is missing to allow the data to be re-used by them. This would be a crucial perspective to also include in WP3’s recommendations.

Another idea would be to involve publishers in the quality control of the metadata published alongside articles. They have the resources to conduct FAIRness-checks upon paper submissions. WP5 could explore this idea for implementing metadata requirements. --

Figure 5. Notes taken by participants during the session on pre-processed eDNA metadata.

Finally, we also discussed the approach of Task 3.2 specifically. Currently, the plan is to align existing standards, use this alignment to identify gaps, and then make recommendations. Instead, we propose (Figure 6) to use the outcome from the use cases to identify the essential metadata and formulate recommendations. Those recommendations can then be mapped and aligned to existing non-DNA standards to identify missing terms and formulate a plan of how to fill gaps in existing data standards for eDNA metadata.

Figure 6. Proposed approach for Task 3.2.

F. Topic 5: Processed eDNA Metadata

Lead: Camila Babo

Scribe: Peter Woollard

Present: Antonio Camacho (UEVG), Pascal Hablützel (VLIZ), Katrina Exter (VLIZ), Peter Woollard (EMBL-EBI) and Camila Babo (BIOPOLIS)

Highlights:

- The automated creation of metadata files within the bioinformatic workflow can ensure easy and relevant reporting.
- Essential metadata fields of bioinformatic pipelines are proposed.
- Solutions ensuring interoperability of standards (field URIs and URLs), metadata schemas (JSON-LD) and reusability of data (standardised output formats) are proposed.
- Minimal metadata and metadata integrity checks by repositories and publishers would increase the trust in data.

The workshop participants contributed to a well-rounded discussion, as they were evenly split between eDNA data producers and repository users on one side (Pascal Hablützel and Antonio Camacho) and eDNA data receivers and managers on the other (Peter Woollard and Katrina Exter). This balance created an exciting opportunity to explore both perspectives on publishing and managing eDNA-derived (meta)data, facilitating a comprehensive discussion and ensuring that the challenges, requirements, and perspectives of both eDNA (meta)data producers and managers were considered. As a result, the workshop identified key concerns and valuable recommendations for effectively handling eDNA metadata.

The discussion was initiated by the question: “Based on your experience, what are the most significant challenges or gaps in the current(meta)data management and sharing practices?”. To aid the discussion, a mind map was prepared to provide an overview of the challenges described in systematic revisions of (meta) data-sharing practices in marine and freshwater environmental DNA metabarcoding studies (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Overview of challenges in eDNA metadata publishing. See Annex 1 for a larger format.

The first and widely agreed challenge was the creation of appropriate and comprehensive metadata. While bioinformatics workflows output data, they rarely output the metadata associated with the pipeline. This condition entails that most users and data publishers manually create this information. Due to limited resources attributed to data curation, most experiments do not include a minimum amount of data needed to reproduce the output data. It became clear that to facilitate the burden of this practice, there should be a minimal metadata process. For example, to resort to tools that enable the automatic creation of metadata files. Participants mentioned BioCompute as an example of a tool that facilitates documentation. BioCompute is a documentation approach, officially published as a standard by the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), aimed at facilitating communication of bioinformatics workflows generated by High-Throughput Sequencing (HTS) between institutions. Some Food and Drug Administration (FDA) Centers have adopted this approach. It promotes interoperability due to its human and machine-readable metadata schema by automatically creating a computation record of a bioinformatics pipeline. The project will soon become an International Organization Standard (ISO) recognised standard [1, 2]. For this kind of implementation to be possible, it is also the responsibility of the developer of the bioinformatic pipelines to publish their product along with a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) both for their work and their profile, for example, through the linkage of an Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID). Both these practices facilitate crediting, therefore supporting the developer's work and possibly promoting the continuous maintenance of the developed tools, given that without property documentation, the constant development of software is hindered, resulting in abandoned projects and a waste of investment [3].

Regarding the attribution of a DOI, participants recommended that the code be published on GitHub and then linked to an external repository that enables the creation of the DOI, such as Zenodo. The idea that code should be tested before its release was also reinforced. As a recommendation, it was stated that unit tests should always accompany tools and that repositories should include badges regarding the testing status to facilitate user recognition of this feature.

The team also discussed which metadata field would be highly relevant to be included in the metadata schema. The following information was proposed: who created the workflow, where the algorithms could be found, which project the workflow was developed for, which version of the code (and its algorithms) was used, which input data was used, which output data was produced, and which parameters and library versions were used. Some of these fields would also include mappings. More specifically,

information such as the internet address of algorithms, data, and creators will be included through URL (Uniform Resource Locator) and persistent identifier (PID) in a subfield. Due to modifications on library versions, it was suggested that a metadata schema be created for each workflow run so that each run would be accurately reproduced [4].

Additionally, each field name should have an associated Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) and a URL containing information such as a description and the required format for that field. It was proposed that metadata schemas follow a JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data (JSON-LD) format [5]. Inserting this information as a URL in the JSON-LD file would enhance interoperability by facilitating system data exchange [6]. The sharing of Docker images that containerised all needed requirements to run the application on which the analysis was run was also suggested. Post-meeting Reflection: If the user is not trained in Bioinformatics, creating a Docker image can be complex.

A significant concern was data and code availability in published papers. When authors incorrectly use data availability statement sections upon paper submissions, crucial information can stay hidden behind paywalls. This practice is often the case when data and software used and produced are only described in the Methodology sections. While this practice is not directly harmful in open-access journals, as this information can still be retrieved, it complicates findability [7].

Data managers also raised concerns over how commonly output data files like Operational Taxonomic Unit (OTU), Amplicon Sequence Variant (ASV), or FASTA had standard formats; however, all had slight differences. In other words, even with these files having a typical structure that most users or pipelines followed, all had their intricacies, making it harder to use these files in a standardised way, as each must be analysed individually and cannot be processed in batches without prior reformatting. It was also recommended that in-house raw sequences be attributed to a Unique Identifier (UID) and that they be made as open as possible (even if not directly, at least via a contact). This practice would allow users to uniquely link the raw sequence with the processed sequences, for example, in OTU files, facilitating sequence tracking when needed.

Following the discussion, it was raised how vital it is to trust metadata. For example, to accurately describe the ecological status of diverse communities of organisms, it is critical to systematically compare environmental and sequence data to analyse the environmental influence on their distribution and variability. Hence, minimal metadata must accompany biological (both -omic and based on classical biological taxonomy), and physicochemical datasets to allow for the development of meta-analyses that integrate diverse methods and the discovery and reusability of this data [8, 9]. It was also noted that some sampling campaigns, such as those performed in Antarctica, request that appropriate metadata accompany the dataset before data publishing. This requirement by campaigns and repositories makes for future-proof data.

Propositions focussed next on whether it would be possible to develop a validation tool that checked data integrity in metadata schemas and whether eDNA repositories should perform further validation to increase trust and reusability. It was stated that eDNA repositories currently validate formats and content. For example, the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) reports that when data is uploaded according to the proposed schema, it undergoes a validation service that allows users to map column headers to asserted field names, checks if any required field is empty, if coordinates are correctly formatted, asserts if coordinates are situated in a marine environment, if data inputted in the date field is valid and if the scientific name of identified species can be matched with World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) [10]. This is a positive example of how repositories can actively participate in the validation of submitted metadata.

Participants registered that, similarly to F-UJI, creating a metric or classification system that evaluates metadata quality would facilitate users' recognition of data reusability. F-UJI is an automated FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data assessment tool that assesses the FAIRness of research data objects [11, 12]. It provides a percentage for the overall FAIRness, also breaking down a classification for each category. These approaches make it straightforward to compare and evaluate guidelines and standards. Despite these advances, there are still limitations involving the validation of

unstructured or free text fields. For these cases, it becomes more complex to perform accurate validation due to high variability and complexity in developing tools that accurately evaluate the context of these entries.

However, while fields that accept URLs still require free text, basic validation is possible if JSON-LD were used as the standard format for metadata schemas. For instance, if a URL were provided for a specific sub-field, such as an ORCID or a software DOI, systems could check if the URL is accessible and verify that the retrieved domain matches expectations. This process would allow systems to assert traceability [13]. Regarding any other fields whose validation would require context, the metadata quality assessment could still be attempted by implementing Language Models (LMs). Current studies have evaluated LMs' performance in automatically extracting domain-specific information to annotate metadata [14, 15].

The discussion concluded with a suggestion to create community-wide events aimed at enhancing the accreditation of bioinformatics tools used in processing eDNA data through the organisation of hackathons. These events would support benchmarking widely used workflows, assist in selecting appropriate pipelines, and help guide the community towards standardised analysis methods. For example, the Critical Assessment of Structure Prediction (CASP) has already achieved this initiative. This community-wide, worldwide experiment established to evaluate the current state of protein structure prediction has occurred every two years since 1994 [16, 17]. Additionally, it was mentioned that such community and worldwide events would be beneficial in reducing duplicated efforts by re-running taxonomic assignments against updated versions of reference databases. As these databases become complete, re-evaluating previous identifications would help ensure the continuous accuracy of identified species and improve the reliability of eDNA-based biomonitoring efforts [18].

Figure 8. Notes taken by participants during the session on processed eDNA metadata.

In summary:

The main raised concerns are:

- Challenges in creating comprehensive metadata records;
- Insufficient resources for manual metadata curation;

- Lack of standardisation in metadata reporting practices;
- Limited metadata detailing bioinformatic tools and workflow runs;
- Underuse of Data Availability Statement for reporting data and code;
- Infrequent attribution of DOIs to bioinformatic tool releases;
- Poor interoperability between data systems;
- Limited trust in reported metadata, negatively impacting data reusability.

The main recommendations proposed throughout the discussion are:

- Make use of documentation approaches that automatically create processed metadata;
- Promote the creation of guidelines for the reporting metadata regarding bioinformatics analysis;
 - Regarding bioinformatic tools, it was proposed that metadata schemas answer the following questions:
 - Who developed the software?
 - Who collaborated in the development of the software?
 - Who should users contact regarding the use of the software?
 - What is the DOI associated with the software release?
 - Which version is associated with the particular release?
 - Was the tool tested before its release?
 - Regarding individual workflow runs, it was proposed that metadata schemas answer the following questions:
 - Which parameters does the workflow use?
 - Which library versions and dependencies does the workflow require?
 - What data object was used as input?
 - What is the internet address of the input data object?
 - What data object was produced as output?
 - What is the internet address of the output data object?
 - These questions should then be associated with standardised field names with an associated URL that contemplates a URI, term description and required format.
- Develop approaches to assign an evaluation metric to available metadata schemas.

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3. Annexes.

Annex 1. Overview of challenges in eDNA metadata publishing (Figure 7).

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